

**EFFECTS OF LOCAL MEDICINAL PLANT HERBA MELILOTI L
EXTRACT ON VASCULAR-PLATELET HEMOSTASIS**

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Abstract. For the first time, the new local preparation consisting of the dry extract of the studied plants has been found to normalize the blood coagulation process based on experiments. When this drug is injected into the body for a long time, it was found that it does not have an adverse effect on the histostructure of vital internal organs of the body and biochemical indicators of peripheral blood. At the same time, the hemostatic effect of ordinary progestin was reduced. As a result, the possibility of using the drug (ordinary contraceptive) in the clinic has been expanded.

Key words: Herba Meliloti L, dry extract, blood, coagulation system, medicinal plants, hemopoiesis.

Introduction. Herba Mileloti L. is a leguminous plant belonging to the Fabaceae family. Medicinal clover or yellow clover (*Melilotus officinalis* L.), white clover (*Melilotus albus* Med) and tall clover (*Melilotus aliissimus* Thuill) are available. The plant is a biennial plant that grows in the mountainous regions of

Tashkent, Samarkand, Fergana, Andijan and Kashkadarya regions on the banks of rivers, streams, gardens and roadsides, and reaches a height of 20-100 cm. When the plant blooms, the upper part of the soil is harvested and the soybean is dried on the ground [97].

Herba Mileloti L. grass and flowers contain 0.8-1% coumarin, coumarin acid, melilotin, melilotonate acid, mellitoside glycoside. The plant also contains fatty and fatty substances, purine compounds, essential oil, choline, mucilage, carotene, vitamin C, E, flavanoids, sugar, dicoumarin and others. The seeds contain 8.5% fatty oil, protein and trigonelline alkaloid [58]. The plant is widespread throughout Europe, Russia, Western Siberia, the Caucasus, Central Asia .

The Herba Mileloti L. plant and medicinal substances obtained from it have been and are being widely used in the medicine of the peoples of the world and in scientific medicine for their diuretic, anti-inflammatory, wound regeneration accelerating, bleeding enhancing and other effects.

A tincture made from the Herba Mileloti L. plant and its flowers is used in Bulgaria for chronic bronchitis, for the prevention of various kidney and urinary bladder pains, for the treatment of arterial blood pressure, migraine, and pathological conditions associated with climax. Cultivated in southern Europe, the leaves and flowers of the saffron are widely used in cooking. It is added to various desserts and cheeses to give it a full flavor. In France, preparations made from this plant and its flowers are used as antispasmodics and anticoagulants, and in cooking - to give flavor and color to culinary products. In Austria, it is called "honey alfalfa" and it is used for stomach and intestinal diseases, chronic bronchitis, and for the purpose of giving aromatic flavor to food. In Germany, the flowering top of the plant was widely used in chronic bronchitis, skin diseases and as a laxative, and in Poland, it was widely used for various headaches, heart palpitations and pain, insomnia, hemorrhoids and other ailments. Herba Mileloti L. is widely used not

only in European countries, but also in Asian countries. For example, in India, decoctions and tinctures of the kashqarbeda plant were used as a laxative, gas expeller, and for bleeding disorders.

Herba Mileloti L. plant was also widely used in the territory of the former Soviet Union. The leaves and flowers of the plant are useful in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases and various convulsive conditions. Its tincture has been used to treat rheumatism, neurasthenia, migraines, and side effects of light therapy.

Herbal tincture was used for bursting purulent wounds, furunculosis, breast inflammation and rheumatism in the joints, washing them, treating them with baths and compresses. The leaves of the plant were crushed and used in the treatment of chronic swellings and as a substance that enhances the regeneration of wounds. It is known that Herba Mileloti L. plant has the ability to stimulate biologically. The biogenic effect of Herba Mileloti L. extract is twice as strong as that of aloe.

Herba Mileloti L. plant and flower are used to sweeten the smell of various tobaccos, in the liquor and beverage industry, to give them and tinctures a pleasant taste. It should be noted that the Herba Mileloti L. plant has the ability to absorb the molybdenum trace element from the soil. That's why molybdenum content in the above-ground part of the plant is 300 times more than its amount in the soil.

The Herba Mileloti L. plant and its flowers have been and are being used on a large scale among the people and in folk medicine in the countries located in the territory of Central Asia. Ibn Sina also showed that Herba Mileloti L. plant is a medicinal plant. Ibn Sina used the leaves of Kashqarba in eye and ear diseases, in the treatment of testicles, uterine tumors and hemorrhoids. He believed that the juice and decoction of the herb caused earaches and headaches, stopped menses, and aborted the fetus. He offered to bathe the patient in kashqarbeda decoction to soothe the itch of the testicles. According to Ibn Sina, "the best of kashqarbeda is

firmer, the color is a little runnier, the taste is more bitter and the smell is more distinct" [1,2,3].

O'.H. Kholmatov and others. ; V. Karimov, A. Shomakhmudov; X.A. Dadaev and K.Kh. According to Khozhimatov et al., Kashqarbeda plant has been and is being used by the people of our Republic and folk medicine for treating wounds, chronic upper respiratory tract diseases, headaches, blood pressure disease, ischemic heart disease, and thrombophlebitis.

Herbal tincture was used as an expectorant in chronic lung disease, as a sedative in neurasthenia, and as a laxative in constipation. X.A. According to Dadaev [4], tincture of the root of *Herba Mileloti L.* gives good results in cases of diabetes and obesity.

H.H. Kholmatov and others. [5] emphasize the use of ointment made from kashqarbeda plant in modern medicine for the treatment of ringworm. Also, these authors note that herbal preparations are also used as anticoagulants.

V. Karimov, A. According to Shomakhmudov [6], crushed fresh leaves of kashqarbeda are applied to sores, sore ears and joints. The leaves and flowers of the plant are also used as a means of removing pus from wounds and accelerating healing. According to the authors, coumarin is the main active ingredient of kashqarbeda in modern medicine. An extract made from *Herba Mileloti L.* herb increases urine output and acts against bacteria, and in experiments, it accelerates the regeneration of rats' livers when a small part of them is cut out.

The drug "Meloncin" is obtained from the leaves of the plant, which is used as a biostimulant in medicine. However, it is impossible to take preparations made from the kashqarbeda plant in large quantities and for a long time. Because fennel is a poisonous plant, using it and its preparations in large doses and over a long period of time weakens the central nervous system, causes

symptoms such as dizziness, nausea and vomiting, insomnia, and can cause liver dysfunction and bleeding [7].

Herba Mileloti L. plant preparations cannot be given to pregnant women, in cases of internal bleeding, and to patients with reduced bleeding time.

Taking into account the above, it is possible to consume the preparations of the kashqarbeda plant only in a certain dose and for a certain period of time, under the supervision and advice of a doctor, in accordance with the laws and regulations of taking the drugs.

In folk medicine, along with the medicinal plant, white clover, white clover (*Melilotus albus* Desr. *Melilotus albus* Medic.) and tall clover, tall clover (*Melilotus altissimus* Thuill) are used. White kashqarbed differs from medicinal kashqarbed in that its flowers are white. Kashqarbe is a 2-year plant that grows up to 1.5 meters in height. The plant is distinguished by its golden yellow flower and is more common in the dense and humid forests and woodlands of Europe.

The research conducted on the chemical composition and pharmacological effects of these species of kashqarbeda showed that its composition, chemical composition and pharmacological effects of medicinal kashqarbeda are similar and close to the biological effects of medicinal kashqarbeda.

The plants of white sedum and tall sedum and their galenic preparations have been and are being used instead of medicinal sedum in the medicine of the people of the world.

Based on the data presented in our literature review, it can be concluded that both studied plants and their preparations (common gojmadaran and Herba Mileloti L.) have diuretic, blood pressure lowering, anti-inflammatory and regenerative effects.

At the same time, common sorghum plant and its preparations speed up the blood clotting time, while *Herba Mileloti L.* plant and its preparations slow down the bleeding time. That is why many research scientists consider it necessary to use the studied medicinal plants in different combinations [8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16].

As we mentioned above, it is used in folk medicine

The purpose of the study.

It consists in studying the effects of a new plant collection (*Herba Meliloti L.*) affecting the blood coagulation process, as well as its pharmacology.

Research methods. Acute toxicity of galenic preparations of studied plants was studied in 36 laboratory mice weighing 17-24 g. The studied preparations (infusion, dry extract) were administered orally using a special metal probe.

The effects of common oleander and kashgarbeda tincture and their 1:1 combination of dry extracts on arterial blood pressure and respiration were studied in 4 rabbits weighing 2.3–3.5 kg using an acute method. For this, experimental animals were anesthetized by intraperitoneal injection of 35-45 mg/kg of 1% ethaminal-sodium solution. Then, under aseptic conditions, the carotid artery, trachea, and leg or ear veins were opened, and the carotid artery was connected to a mercury Ludwig monometer, and the trachea was connected to the Marea capsule through a special device.

Results and its discussion. in the experiments, the effects of the dry extracts of the studied plants and the collection of extracts composed of them on the general process of blood coagulation and vascular hemostasis were studied. In this experiment, we focused on the thromboelastogram indicators recorded on the Thromb-2 thromboelastograph. The effects of the drugs on blood vessels - platelet hemostasis, the number of platelets in peripheral blood, adhesion, aggregation and changes in the amount of retraction of clotted blood were determined.

Blood was taken from the experimental animals for analysis before administration of drugs and at 30, 60 and 120 minutes of the experiment. Taking into account that in previous experiments, the most optimal and good results were obtained when the drugs were administered in doses of 100 mg/kg, in this series of experiments, the drugs were administered orally at a single dose of 100 mg/kg. The obtained results are presented in the table.

Effect of dry extract on primary vascular-platelet hemostasis (M±m;n=6)

Blood clotting indicators	Time after administration of the drug, in minutes				
	normally	30'	60'	120'	After 1 day
Platelets 109/l	350±24	500±35*	500±45*	400±35	400±35
Clot retraction, per minute	40±4,0	32±4,0	28±2,0	33±2,0	36±2,0
Platelet adhesion, in %	20±2,4	46±3,0*	33±2,4*	22±2,0*	25±2,4
Spontaneous aggregation, in %	32±2,4	64±4,6*	35±2,4	30±2,6	33±2,6

Note: *R < 0.05 relative to the norm

According to the data presented in this table, the dry extract of the common oleander plant at the studied dose (100 mg/kg) increased the amount of platelets in the peripheral blood by 43% in the 30th and 60th minutes of the experiment, and compared to the norm (350±24·109/l) by 500±35, respectively. and was 500±45·109/l. By the 120th minute of the experiment, the amount of platelets in the peripheral blood was close to the norm and equaled 400±35·109/l. At the same time, the dry extract of the common oleander plant at a dose of 100 mg/kg increases the functional activity of platelets in peripheral blood and increases platelet adhesion by 46±3.0% in the 30th minute of the experiment, and by 33±2.4% in the 60th minute. This change returns to normal at the 120th minute of the experiment and is equal to 22±2.0%.

Conclusion: Cardiovascular diseases are increasing in the elderly, even among young people. The staff of used the common oleander plant and its flower tincture, which is used in folk medicine, as a diuretic and hypotensive drug. But this plant increases the blood clotting process due to the presence of endogenous substance Vitamin K. As a result, urinary excretion disorders, increased blood coagulation and related pathological processes are recorded. Taking into account the above, the herbal tincture under study has a diuretic and hypotensive effect, but it slightly accelerates the process of blood clotting in elderly patients. This limited the possibility of using this drug on a large scale. Because the blood coagulation process is increased compared to the norm in the diseases of atherosclerosis, hypertension, thrombosis, rheumatic arthritis, heart and kidney failure in our elderly.

Therefore, if the blood coagulation-accelerating effect of the preparation of common oleander plant is reduced, it can be easily used in cardiovascular diseases.

For this purpose, a 1:1 mixture was prepared by mixing kashqarbeda plant, which slows down the blood clotting process, and ordinary buymadoron plant, which is widely used in folk medicine. We have thoroughly studied the pharmacology of the new plant collection and their preparations by adding the dry extract of the kashgarbeda plant, which has the ability to slow down the blood coagulation process, to the dry extract of the ordinary bojmadaran plant, which is recommended for wide use in medicine.

List of used literature

1. Farmonova N.T., Aliev H.U., Urmonova F.F. K pharmacology of novogo rastitelnogo sbora mochegonnogo deystviya. // Proceedings of the scientific and practical conference on the topic "Current problems of education, science and production in pharmacy". - Tashkent, 2005. - P.178-179.
2. Khodzhimatov K.H., Aproside G.S., Khadzhimatov A.K. Dikorastushchie tselebnye rasteniya Sredney Azii. - Tashkent: Ibn Sino, 1995. -112 p.

3. Kholmatov O'.Kh., Akhmedov O'.A. Pharmacognosy. - Tashkent: Ibn Sino, 1995.-87
4. Kholmatov O'.Kh., Doschanov B.O., Sobirov R.S. Medicinal plants used by Abu Ali ibn Sina.- Urganch:UDU, 2003. -179 p.
5. Non-narcotic analgesics and poragenia slizistoy obolochki zheludka i dvenadtsatiperstnoy kishki. // Clinical pharmacology and therapy.-Moscow, 2000.- No. 5. -S.54-56.
6. Yunuskhojaev A.N. Oslojnenie mekarstvennoy therapy. // Health care in Uzbekistan.-Tashkent, 2005.- No. 1.-B.5-7.
7. 104. *Achillea filipendulina* Lam. A new prospective medicinal plant of Uzbekistan flora.//D.K. Pulatova, F.F. Urmanova, Kh. M. Komilov, S.I. Iskanderov.// Abstracts of the Third International Symposium on Chemistry of Natural Compounds (SCNC) - Bukhara, 1998. - R.20.Djanaev G. Y. et al. PHARMACOTHERAPEUTIC EFFECTIVENESS OF HERBAL MEDICINE" YAZVANOL" IN THE EXPERIMENTAL INDOMETHACINE GASTROPATY MODEL //World Bulletin of Public Health. – 2023. – T. 21. – C. 144-147.
8. Джанаев Г. Ю. Уткир токсик гепатитда глицерамнинг сафро ва унинг таркибидаги моддаларнинг экскрециясига таъсирини ўрганиш. – 2020.
9. YU, D. G., & ALLAYEVA, M. (2022). ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ НОВОГО ПРЕПАРАТА СЭЛР В ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИИ ГАСТРОПАТИЙ.
- 10.Djanaev, G. Y., Khakimov, Z. Z., Allaeva, M. J., Makhsumov Sh, M., Zaytseva, O. A., & Mamadjanova, M. A. Comparative Study of the Influence of Lesbochole. *Misoprostol and Mucagen on the Gastric Mucous Barrier in Indometacin Gastropathy.*
- 11.Гиляревский С.Р. Обеспечение безопасности применения диуретиков при лечении сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний: роль калий сберегающих диуретиков. // Фарматека.-Москва, 2004. -№ 8, -С.70-74.

12. Гуревич К.Г. Дискуссионные вопросы эффективности и безопасности лекарственных средств растительного происхождения. // Фарматека-Москва, 2003-№ 5,- С.71-79.
13. Дадаев. Х.А. Безлекарственные методы лечения. –Ташкент:Ибн Сино, 1995. -112 с.
14. Денисов И.Н., Шевченко Ю.Л., Назыров Ф.Г. Клинические рекомендации и фармакологический справочник., М.:ГЭОТАР-Медиа, 2005.- 1184с.
15. Закирова Н.И. Кардиотропное действие суммы буфадиенолидов-бакагина в возрастном аспекте.//Автореф. дисс. ... канд. мед. наук. -Ташкент:ТМА.2006.-20 с.
16. Ибрагимов Н.И. Первые фармакологические исследование и гемостатические свойства лагохилусов Проскорякова и Ферганского // Автореф. дис... канд. мед.наук,.-Краснодар. 1974, -22 с.